

Some arithmetical properties of primitive numbers of power p^1

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is to study the arithmetical properties of the primitive numbers of power p by using the elementary method, and give some interesting identities and asymptotic formulae.

Keywords Primitive numbers of power p ; Smarandache function; Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

Let p be a fixed prime and n be a positive integer. The primitive numbers of power p , denoted as $S_p(n)$, is defined as following:

$$S_p(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, p^n | m!\}.$$

In problem 47,48 and 49 of [1], Professor F.Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the primitive numbers sequences $\{S_p(n)\}(n = 1, 2, \dots)$. It is clear that $\{S_p(n)\}(n = 1, 2, \dots)$ is the sequence of multiples of prime p and each number being repeated as many times as its exponent of power p is. What's more, there is a very close relationship between this sequence and the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$, where

$$S(n) = \min\{m : m \in N, n | m!\}.$$

Many scholars have studied the properties of $S(n)$, see [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6]. It is easily to show that $S(p) = p$ and $S(n) < n$ except for the cases $n = 4$ and $n = p$. Hence, the following relationship formula is obviously:

$$\pi(x) = -1 + \sum_{n=2}^{[x]} \left[\frac{S(n)}{n} \right],$$

where $\pi(x)$ denotes the number of primes up to x , and $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer less than or equal to x . However, it seems no one has given some nontrivial properties about the primitive number sequences before. In this paper, we studied the relationship between the Riemann zeta-function and an infinite series involving $S_p(n)$, and obtained some interesting identities and asymptotic formulae for $S_p(n)$. That is, we shall prove the following conclusions:

Theorem 1. For any prime p and complex number s , we have the identity:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p^s(n)} = \frac{\zeta(s)}{p^s - 1},$$

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where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function.

Specially, taking $s = 2, 4$ and $p = 2, 3, 5$, we have the

Corollary. The following identities hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_2^2(n)} &= \frac{\pi^2}{18}; & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_3^2(n)} &= \frac{\pi^2}{48}; & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_5^2(n)} &= \frac{\pi^2}{144}; \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_2^4(n)} &= \frac{\pi^4}{1350}; & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_3^4(n)} &= \frac{\pi^4}{7200}; & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_5^4(n)} &= \frac{\pi^4}{56160}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. Let p be any fixed prime. Then for any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p(n)} = \frac{1}{p-1} \left(\ln x + \gamma + \frac{p \ln p}{p-1} \right) + O(x^{-\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}),$$

where γ is the Euler constant, ϵ denotes any fixed positive number.

Theorem 3. Let k be any positive integer. Then for any prime p and real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} S_p^k(n) = \frac{x^{k+1}}{(k+1)(p-1)} + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}).$$

§2. Proof of the theorems

To complete the proof of the theorems, we need a simple Lemma.

Lemma. Let b, T are two positive numbers, then we have

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} \frac{a^s}{s} ds = \begin{cases} 1 + O\left(a^b \min\left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln a}\right)\right), & \text{if } a > 1; \\ O\left(a^b \min\left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln a}\right)\right), & \text{if } 0 < a < 1; \\ \frac{1}{2} + O\left(\frac{b}{T}\right), & \text{if } a = 1. \end{cases}$$

Proof. See Lemma 6.5.1 of [8].

Now we prove the theorems. First, we prove Theorem 1. Let $m = S_p(n)$, if $p^\alpha \parallel m$, then the same number m will repeat α times in the sequence $S_p(n)$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$). Noting that $S_p(n)$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$) is the sequence of multiples of prime p , we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p^s(n)} &= \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ p^\alpha \parallel m}}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha}{m^s} = \sum_{p^\alpha} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,p)=1}}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha}{p^{\alpha s} m^s} \\ &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha}{p^{\alpha s}} \zeta(s) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \zeta(s) \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha}{p^{\alpha s}}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{p^s}\right) \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha}{p^{\alpha s}} = \frac{1}{p^s} + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^{(\alpha+1)s}} = \frac{1}{p^s} + \frac{1}{p^s} \left(\frac{1}{p^s - 1}\right) = \frac{1}{p^s - 1},$$

we have the identity

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p^s(n)} = \frac{\zeta(s)}{p^s - 1}.$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Now we prove Theorem 2 and Theorem 3. Let $x \geq 1$ be any real number. If we set $a = \frac{x}{S_p(n)}$ in the lemma, then we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} \frac{x^s}{S_p^{s-k}(n)s} ds \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} S_p^k(n) + O \left(\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} \frac{x^b}{S_p^{b-k}(n)} \min \left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln \left(\frac{x}{S_p(n)} \right)} \right) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) > x}}^{\infty} \frac{x^s}{S_p^{s-k}(n)s} ds = O \left(\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) > x}}^{\infty} \frac{x^b}{S_p^{b-k}(n)} \min \left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln \left(\frac{x}{S_p(n)} \right)} \right) \right), \quad (2)$$

where k is any integer. Combining (1) and (2), we find

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} \frac{x^s}{s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p^{s-k}(n)} ds \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} S_p^k(n) + O \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^b}{S_p^{b-k}(n)} \min \left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln \left(\frac{x}{S_p(n)} \right)} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Then from Theorem 1, we can get

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} S_p^k(n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{b-iT}^{b+iT} \frac{\zeta(s-k)x^s}{(p^{s-k} - 1)s} ds + O \left(x^b \min \left(1, \frac{1}{T \ln \left(\frac{x}{S_p(n)} \right)} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Now we calculate the first term in the right side of (4).

When $k = -1$, taking $b = \frac{1}{2}$ and $T = x$, we move the integral line from $s = \frac{1}{2} + iT$ to $s = -\frac{1}{2} + iT$. This time, the function

$$f(s) = \frac{\zeta(s+1)x^s}{(p^{s+1} - 1)s}$$

have a second order pole point at $s = 0$. Its residue is $\frac{1}{p-1} \left(\ln x + \gamma - \frac{p \ln p}{p-1} \right)$. Hence, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} \frac{\zeta(s+1)x^s}{(p^{s+1} - 1)s} ds \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} \left(\ln x + \gamma - \frac{p \ln p}{p-1} \right) + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{-\frac{1}{2}-iT} + \int_{-\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{-\frac{1}{2}+iT} + \int_{-\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+1)x^s}{(p^{s+1} - 1)s} ds. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

We can easily get the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{-\frac{1}{2}-iT} + \int_{-\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+iT} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+1)x^s}{(p^{s+1}-1)s} ds \right| \\ & \ll \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \frac{\zeta(\sigma+1+iT)x^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(p^{\sigma+1+iT}-1)T} \right| d\sigma \ll \frac{x^{\frac{1}{2}}}{T} = x^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{-\frac{1}{2}+iT} \frac{\zeta(s+1)x^s}{(p^{s+1}-1)s} ds \right| \ll \int_0^T \left| \frac{\zeta(\frac{1}{2}+it)x^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{(p^{\frac{1}{2}+it}-1)(\frac{1}{2}+t)} \right| dt \ll x^{-\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}. \quad (7)$$

Combining (4), (5), (6) and (7), we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{S_p(n)} = \frac{1}{p-1} \left(\ln x + \gamma + \frac{p \ln p}{p-1} \right) + O(x^{-\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}).$$

This is the result of Theorem 2.

When $k \geq 1$, taking $b = k + \frac{3}{2}$ and $T = x$, we move the integral line of (4) from $s = k + \frac{3}{2}$ to $s = k + \frac{1}{2}$. Now the function

$$g(s) = \frac{\zeta(s-k)x^s}{(p^{s-k}-1)s}$$

have a simple pole point at $s = k + 1$ with residue $\frac{x^{k+1}}{(p-1)(k+1)}$. Using the same method we can also get

$$\sum_{\substack{n=1 \\ S_p(n) \leq x}}^{\infty} S_p^k(n) = \frac{x^{k+1}}{(k+1)(p-1)} + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\epsilon}).$$

This completes the proofs of the theorems.

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